

Resolution: Museums, Communities and Sustainability

A reconsideration of the *Round Table on the role of museums in today's Latin America* (1972) involving key representatives of ICOM and published as *Declaration of Santiago de Chile* (UNESCO, 1973), suggests it is opportune for the international museum community to recognize the significance of the *integral* museum concept as a means of assisting communities and their efforts to ensure the sustainability of their heritages.

Noting that the *Recommendation concerning the Protection and Promotion of Museums and Collections, their Diversity and their Role in Society* (UNESCO, 2015) confirms the significance and contemporary relevance of the 1973 Declaration, and,

Acknowledging that since 1973, museums have evolved to adopt different concepts and practices that have recognised community museology and promoted greater awareness of the social role of museums, and,

Reconfirming ICOM's Resolutions relating to communities, sustainability and cultural landscapes, and noting that the ICOM Resolution concerning the "extended museum" adopted in Milan in 2016 underlined that museums are more than traditional buildings, collections and established curatorial practices, having value for social, cultural, environmental and economic development, thereby furthering the aims of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, and,

Recognising that although community museums are vital actors for *social, environmental and cultural* inclusion and transformative sustainability in the 21st Century, and that communities may have meaningful autonomy over decision making in their museums and local heritage management, it is evident they often lack adequate recognition and professional and economic support, and,

Recognising the effective approach, research methods and shared values deployed in the Horizon 2020 EU-LAC-MUSEUMS project (<http://www.eulacmuseums.net>; Grant Agreement number 693669) towards supporting the development of community-based museums at local and bilateral levels for intra-regional and bi-regional integration:

It is recommended by the 34th Ordinary General Assembly of ICOM, meeting 1-7 September 2019 in Kyoto, Japan, that the newly elected President and the Executive Council:

- (a) Provide greater recognition of, and support for, the vast number of community-led organisations that do not currently fulfil the ICOM Definition of a Museum (2007) but that further the goals of safeguarding and promoting access to natural, cultural and intangible heritages and their sustainable use for environmental, social and economic development of communities, towards achievement of the UN 2030 goals and climate justice.
- (b) Remain sensitive to local and regional differences, and demonstrate awareness of the geo-political dimension of the concept of the Museum, especially relating to the resource needs of community-based museums in lower to middle income countries.
- (c) Recognize the value of community-based museums for the promotion of ICOM, UNESCO and international charter instruments and their values of human rights and peace, and sustainable community development in general, especially in the contexts of indigenous and ethnic minority communities, and in the face of the challenges posed by migration.
- (d) Encourage collaborative work with and between community-based museums on national and bi-regional levels.
- (e) Contribute to building the capacity of community-based museums and ecomuseums in their transformative approaches towards sustainable living communities and territorial development and the protection and enhancement of cultural landscapes.
- (f) Strengthen, enable and mobilise ICOM National and International Committees, as well as Regional Alliances and Affiliated Organisations, to act as mediators for cultural understanding at the community level and between regions to achieve the above goals.

Submitted by the ICOM Europe and ICOM LAC Regional Alliances on 19 April 2019.

Resolution No. 5

“Museums, Communities and Sustainability”

Noting the Declaration of Santiago de Chile (UNESCO, 1973), reconfirming ICOM’s Resolutions relating to communities, sustainability and cultural landscapes, and noting that the ICOM Resolution concerning the “extended museum” adopted in Milan in 2016 underlined that museums are more than traditional buildings, collections and established curatorial practices, having value for social, cultural, environmental and economic development, thereby furthering the aims of the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals, and,

The 34th General Assembly recommends ICOM to:

- provide greater recognition of, and support for, the vast number of community-led organisations that do not currently fulfil the ICOM Definition of a Museum (2007) but that further the goals of safeguarding and promoting access to natural, cultural and intangible heritages and their sustainable use for environmental, social and economic development of communities, towards achievement of the UN 2030 goals and climate justice;
- remain sensitive to local and regional differences, and demonstrate awareness of the geo-political dimension of the concept of the Museum, especially relating to the resource needs of community-based museums in lower to middle income countries;
- recognize the value of community-based museums for the promotion of ICOM, UNESCO and international charter instruments and their values of human rights and peace, and sustainable community development in general, especially in the contexts of indigenous and ethnic minority communities, and in the face of the challenges posed by migration;
- encourage collaborative work with and between community-based museums on national and bi-regional levels;
- contribute to building the capacity of community-based museums and ecomuseums in their transformative approaches towards sustainable living communities and territorial development and the protection and enhancement of cultural landscapes; and
- strengthen, enable and mobilise ICOM National and International Committees, as well as Regional Alliances and Affiliated Organisations, to act as mediators for cultural understanding at the community level and between regions to achieve the above goals.

NB: Drafted from a recommendation submitted by ICOM Europe and ICOM LAC.

The voting results of the resolution on *"Museums, Communities and Sustainability"* at the ICOM Summit in Kyoto, Japan, September 2019 (389 "yes", 35 "no", 21. "abstain", 116 "no vote")